

How Modern Propaganda Evolves Around the Society?

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Abstract

Propaganda has shaped the world over the years. It has also evolved according to the differences of ideologies that have changed and strengthened over the years. Modern propaganda has been evolving towards modernization before the 60's and heavily influenced by great wars. Strong propaganda techniques, which are mostly shaped around leaders and ideologies, started to be shaped around civil right movements and the power of the world press, especially after the 60s (after the Great Wars). Modern propaganda, which evolved with the developing technology, started to show its effect with the masses on a global scale. Today, modern propaganda, which is now completely global, has a very strong impact on people with some methods such as cinema, media and organizations worldwide.

Keywords: Modern propaganda, Civil rights movement, Great wars, Leaders, Societies, Media

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INTRODUCTION

In the daily life, we confront with the confrontation of different ideologies in the plenty of medium. By the changes in medium, the shape and effects of it constantly changing. These effects in close relation with the propaganda and its tools to make its affect huge are evolved in the history gradually. The biggest leap in the timeline is the era of cold war and the afterward historical events which comes after the win of the United States of America (USA). "liberal policies". The war of the propaganda from World War I (WWI) to the today's world show us how modern propaganda evolved (Fox&Welch, 2012).

World War I (WWI)

Propaganda is regularly deployed as a method to influence people outside conflicts, as well, in particular by hard-line political regimes. And many forms of communication from democratic governments, such as health-awareness campaigns, could be classed as propaganda (Fox & Welch, 2012). Although there were some precedents for war propaganda involving the media dating back to the early 19th century (and war propaganda itself is as old as history), the First World War was the first war in which belligerent governments deliberately created organisations to generate and direct propaganda at their enemies, at their allies, at neutrals, and at their own populations, as an essential part of the way that they waged war (Welch, 2014a).

The armies of continental Europe were made up of conscripts, who really had little choice about going to war. In 1914 the British Army, by contrast, was made up of professionals and then volunteers. The British placed immense reliance, therefore, on propaganda to justify the war to the people, to help promote recruitment into the armed forces and to convince the population that their sacrifices would be rewarded. As David Welch (2014) stated that “One of the most enduring images of the war - much copied and parodied since - remains the distinctive recruitment poster of Lord Kitchener’s heavily mustachioed face and intimidating finger imploring the British population that ‘Your Country Needs YOU’ ” (Welch, 2014b) (Picture 1).

Picture 1. Your Country Needs YOU (<https://www.bl.uk/world-war-one/articles/patriotism-and-nationalism>)

British recruitment posters changed in tone, from appealing to an individual’s honour to ‘mobilisation by shame’. Savile Lumley’s famous poster of 1915 depicted two young children asking their father about his military prowess after the war: ‘Daddy, what did YOU do in the Great War?’ The emotional blackmail of using children to shame their elders into fighting was, in fact, employed by most of the

belligerents. Women were also assigned the responsibility for ordering men into war. Perhaps the most well known in this genre is ‘Women of Britain Say- “GO!”’ (Picture 3). They found an alternative to manipulate public by showing the propaganda on everyday circulation items such as coins, banknotes, postage stamps or symbolic structures such as statues and also the most effective ones; national anthems and nation’s flag (Welch, 2014b).

Picture 2. Two little children asking their father what he did in the war

(<https://www.bl.uk/world-war-one/articles/patriotism-and-nationalism>)

Picture 3. The women of Britain who say go to war (<https://www.bl.uk/world-war-one/articles/patriotism-and-nationalism>)

The need to raise money to pay for the war by means of war bonds (or ‘Liberty Bonds’ as they were known in the United States) provided one of the most important patriotic themes for posters and for the new medium of film. A recurring, related theme was the portrayal of money (coins and banknotes) as an active force in military engagement, for example: ‘Turn Your Silver into Bullets - at the Post Office’. In France, a similar poster, designed by Jules Abel Faivre in 1915, depicted a large gold coin with a Gallic cockerel on it, crushing a German soldier, with the slogan: ‘Deposit Your Gold for France - Gold Fights for Victory’. All sides, therefore, supplemented their military engagement with propaganda aimed at stimulating national sentiment by means of nationalistic slogans and patriotic calls to arms (Welch, 2014b).

World War II (WWII)

As she said that “Ralph Casey considered propaganda an “instrument of the devil”⁶¹ where the propagandist intentionally deceives, lies, and falsifies facts” (Wilcott, 2013). One of the most expected explanations for what is propaganda is usually an attempt to negatively manipulate people. In October 1929, the American big depression started with the stock market crashing, and this put the entire world in an economic crisis which did not still recover from WWI. In the meantime Adolf Hitler started to dominate his power in Germany and Germany started to rebuild its power in central Europe to fade their embarrassed peace agreement from WWI (Foley, 2015). When the second great war started the Propaganda Department of the USA, the Office of Facts and Figures was established to discuss the need of the United States to support the Western Allies ,but organization wasn’t moving as a whole (Wilcott, 2013) (Picture 4).

Picture 4. USA Government propaganda poster, 1943 (Government Printing Office for the Office of Price Administration, NARA Still Picture Branch (NWDNS-188-PP-42).

American President, Franklin D. Roosevelt implemented a temporary strategy in which he sent aid to the Allies in the form of military supplies which progressively increased, and it seemed clear to many Americans either that way or this way they’ll be joining the war (Wilcott, 2013).

Therefore, the government created two psychological warfare departments: “one for the white propaganda, the Office of War Information and other one for the black propaganda the Office of Strategic Services responsible (Foley, 2015). After a while all Japanese assets in the United States got frozen and implemented an oil embargo which intended to deprive Japan from war enthusiasm which they displeased by the actions of the US, Japan agreed to enter into negotiations (Wilcott, 2013). On the other hand while the negotiations started, Japanese launched an attack on the American naval base at Pearl Harbor and lost more than 2,500 people. Then President Roosevelt made his famous speech and called for Congress to declare war on Japan and then officially declare war against Germany, although it had been supporting the Allied effort for some time (Foley, 2015).

As he stated that “The American people were united by their anger and sense of patriotism following the devastating attack on Pearl Harbor.” The Americans learned their enemies and the goals of the war were clear for the most part, as well. Mostly these ideas were imposed by propaganda to the Americans to free conquered nations, to rescue victims of persecution, and to extract revenge against the Japanese (Foley, 2015) (Picture 5).

Picture 5. World War II propaganda poster (<http://chumpfish3.blogspot.com/2010/03/this-is-enemy.html>)

As the war goes, objectives get simpler so the government could advocate on behalf of continued action and drum up support for the war (Foley, 2015). They hugely advocate of consuming less saving more for instance; if someone was seen driving around alone that could hurt his or her reputation, and no one wanted to be accused of not backing the American war effort wholeheartedly in the fight for freedom against the enemy regimes abroad. To increase the war callings masculinity and strength for both men and women exposed to the public (Foley, 2015). At the end of the war all the people who joined the war were manipulated/attracted by the similar thoughts and motivations of securing their homeland, their right as a nation etc. The propaganda done mostly by the government which directed people for not their behalf mostly like herds (Picture 6).

Pictur 6. World War II propaganda poster

(https://www.docsteach.org/images/documents/513519/orig_513519_2679.jpg?v=u6mqZkE4Q)

How was the Modern Propaganda in Reconstruction of Europe?

Marshall Plan

At the end of the war, the only thing that was left was depression across Europe. The fundamental problem wasn't the labor, due to fast population losses. It was money and other resources. After fascism's failure, the United States offered a vision of modernization which was unprecedented in its power, internationalism and invitation to emulation. The European Recovery Program was one of the strong ways to capitalise these ideas, but to convince the US citizens government started a propaganda program. Marshall Plan films were a US propaganda triumph as they reinforced Hollywood's old message of America's high standard of living (Ellwood, 2003). In March 1947, United States president Harry Truman unveiled what became known as the Truman Doctrine, pledging US support for European countries so they could exercise self-determination and resist a communist takeover (Llewellyn & Thompson, 2020). The left-wing in America and elsewhere condemned the Marshall Plan as an attempt to strengthen the grip of US-led capitalism on Western Europe. Llewellyn says that "*As this French image suggests, not all were happy with American aid to post-war Europe*"(Llewellyn & Thompson, 2020) (Picture 7).

Picture 8. Poster of not everyone's dissatisfaction with American aid to post-war Europe

(<https://alphahistory.com/coldwar/marshall-plan/>)

Soviet and Austrian Communist propaganda regularly blasted the “Marshallization” of Europe, namely the enslavement of the European economy by American imperialists. Obviously the United States wasn’t helping without expecting a major return in the future. First of all, the barrier to Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) to avoid it to come inside the Europe and secondly Governmental change in Europe to liberal-democratic systems like the United States which will speed up the global trade, make American companies profit, recover Europe, and suppress the counter propaganda of USSR and left wings inside the USA. The Marshall Plan was cleverly marketed by the American government as a generous and visionary policy, to allow the rebuilding of Europe (Picture 9). The conditions on Marshall Plan funds, however, were not publicly advertised. Moreover the US offered European Recovery Program (ERP) aid to the Soviet Union and Soviet-bloc countries, knowing that the conditions would make it impossible for them to accept by doing that the value of propaganda spread across the whole world. Lastly, one of the most important investments for the U.S. via Marshall plan is popularizing the usage of the U.S. dollar which will lead it to become the world's reserve currency (Table 1) (Llewellyn & Thompson, 2020).

Table 1. Top eight recipient nations of Marshall Plan funds (US dollars)

Nations	1948/49	1949/50	1950/51	Total
United Kingdom	\$1316m	\$921m	\$1060m	\$3297m
France	\$1085m	\$691m	\$520m	\$2296m
Germany	\$510m	\$438m	\$500m	\$1448m
Italy	\$594m	\$405m	\$205m	\$1204m
Netherlands	\$471m	\$302m	\$355m	\$1128m
Belgium/Luxembourg	\$195m	\$222m	\$360m	\$777m
Austria	\$232m	\$166m	\$70m	\$468m

Denmark	\$103m	\$87m	\$195m	\$385m
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Picture 9. "Rebuilding Europe," Marshall Plan poster from France, ca. 1950

Shadow of Communism

Media usage under the Soviet influence has long been associated at the very first with propaganda. As she says “The USSR-the world’s first “propaganda state” to use Peter Kenez’s term established a radical new communications order that would be widely emulated.” and “The Bolshevik regime,” wrote Kenez in an influential 1985 study, “was the first not merely to set itself propaganda goals but also through political education to aim to create a new humanity suitable for living in a new society” (Roth-Ey, 2015).

There's no more efficient way to shape the minds of the next generation than in the classroom. Schools across the country had political shrines, marches, songs and pledges of allegiance dedicated to Soviet leadership. Primarily a tactic to reach the illiterate, radio receivers was placed in communal places where the poor gathered to hear news. Whenever war was imminent, the Soviet government used propaganda films to prepare and inspire the populace, but they weren't just shown in theaters. For citizens without the means to pay for theater admission, films and newsreels were shown on the walls of subway stations and propaganda trains. Meetings and lectures made the masses feel important and well informed. They instilled solidarity, kept people up-to-date on news and provided instruction on the proper way of life. Immediately after coming to power, the Communist Party suppressed all newspapers that opposed them and kept unfavorable stories from being published (Roth-Ey, 2015).

There were even studies of the government on what and how their propaganda affects the public and what are the confluences of this (Picture 10). While the cold war showed itself in the late 1940s, the

problem of propaganda now it is considered as sponsorship of the government for “psychological” warfare became a major subject. As she stated that “The main lines of what would later be dubbed a “totalitarian” school in Soviet studies presented a model of the Soviet regime as resting on the dual pillars of propaganda and repression or, in Lenin’s terms, “on a balance between coercion and persuasion” (Roth-Ey, 2015) (Picture 11).

To sum up, the major problem of building foundation to Soviet Union is the main cause of these propagandas. The need for propaganda is obvious as a glue to the whole nation. As Lenin indicates, “...coercion and persuasion” because it is the only way (V.I.Lenin, Collected Works).

Picture 10. Poster child of the USSR: Gagarin, the first man in space (<https://www.rbth.com/history/330138-this-soviet-propaganda-portrays-gagarin>)

Picture 11. Viktor Denisov’s “Comrade Lenin Sweeps the Earth of the Unclean”

(https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Propaganda_in_the_Soviet_Union#/media/File:Dyadya_lenin.jpg)

Antiracist Propaganda in America at 60's

Modern Propaganda has changed dimensions after World War II. International diplomacy had become an element of propaganda after Wilson Principles. It is emphasized that a book by Newman, *Modern Propaganda* started to be made with public action. The situation of black people in America was an ideal example of this. According to him in the 60's, there was some strong antiracist propaganda for the rights of black people in America. Black Americans had a lot of trouble with social prejudices. They weren't even allowed to vote, and it was now taking place in the world press. Newman added, the world press effects and public actions deeply intensified so national unrest was uprising and fight has been starting between white and black (Newman, 2004). Therewithal, public protests, which emerged with the courage of the world press, were serious propaganda for politicians and a new civil law proposal was made at the congress in the early 60's. Therefore, everyone has the right to vote, with some troublesome rules and national unrest was starting to relieve. Modern propaganda showed its power in Amerika with that way. However, the effect of all short-term solutions was short because the system did not change and minds were still the same. The actions of the people with various methods became propaganda to the world this time and international law had to intervene in this situation. Because of all of these, presidential candidates are directly affected. In fact, these kinds of modern propagandas helped Kennedy, who was the legendary president of America, become president. In other words, modern propaganda has evolved to rise above the leaders, and with the development of technology, it has gathered masses around it through the press and thus, popular actions emerge and affect the courts. Therefore, courts had to affect the politicians. All in all, modern propaganda began to grow stronger with global popular support. After World War II, some countries got stronger and the globalist trend started evolving modern propaganda methods. By the way, the re-strengthening of the globalism trend in America also enabled the modern propaganda methods that evolved to hit America first (Palloshi, 2015).

Civil Rights Movements with Developing Alternative Media at 90's

The 90's were the rise of multiculturalism and alternative media. Therefore, modern propaganda has begun to show its strength globally through the public. An ideology that shows itself at one end of the world could spread all over the world. The civil rights movements in America have been starting to be successful with the power of modern propaganda. Black people first gained their rights as governors and councilors. Thus, they started to gather stronger supporters to make their voices heard with the development of media in the 90's. Their propaganda had a worldwide impact as Mae Carol Jemison was the first black person to participate in the space program that many countries were working and paying on. After that, art became one of the methods of modern propaganda and an art movement could easily spread all over the world with the advancing technological possibilities. It is emphasized that a book by Iron, art was the only method which people could have to declare their noise and he added art was a really strong way to make propaganda with both political and civil ways. Even, the art has been as effective as a weapon on racism in America and has a worldwide impact on the civil rights of black people (Iton, 2008).

After the effects of art, films have started to be used to make propaganda with the developing film industry. Thus, modern propaganda has increased its power with things people enjoyed. Modern propaganda was able to spread necessary messages to the whole world, first with the pictures and visuals people loved so much, then with the cinemas that people loved to go to. However, this time the

character of messages started to lose its importance. Everything good or bad, useful or harmful, right or wrong came to people's minds with a good movie. This effect of modern propaganda would begin to become a global security issue in the future (Asmolov, 2019).

Alternative Media and Developing Technology Affects

Everything has changed dimensions nowadays. The Internet has become the center of life. While modern propaganda was extremely politically effective with the alternative media that developed in the 90s, thousands of supporters can be gathered for any ideology within seconds now. Therefore, any civil injustice in the world cannot be concealed and it is spreading all over the world. It is such a spread that politicians cannot remain silent and have to intervene. It is mentioned that an article by Seo, an image shared on social media is uploaded to the world's pockets in seconds and people get involved immediately. It means modern propaganda is starting to evolve visual propaganda. Therefore, any visual methods can be used on social media for any events or any ideologies. Even countries share their bombing, attacking or defending images on social media. Thus, they are affecting people globally with visual propaganda (Seo, 2014).

On the other hand, when politicians want to use an idea or an ideology against each other, they immediately resort to modern propaganda and social media. Therefore, they have thousands of supporters. However, It is really hard to understand whether the posts are true or false. People began to be deceived so easily that millions of people started to gather behind a lie with a text under an image. It is mentioned that a book by Barclay, a twenty eight years old man from America walked into Washington and then, he shot someone with three bullets. He lied about Hillary Clinton as the reason for shooting when he was arrested. His story leaked to the press and created a fake news worldwide phenomenon. Barclay added, modern propaganda with developing technology is so dangerous for everyone and fake news spreads in seconds. Thus, the world is rising around a lie (Barclay, 2018).

Artificial Intelligence Affects

Modern propaganda continues to progress globally with advanced alternative media in two ways. Firstly, it began to culturally gather the whole world under one culture and secondly, it started using artificial intelligence as a method. Artificial intelligence will be the main method of modern propaganda. Social media bots are guiding people on social media nowadays. A post can be boosted with bots and can appear before the whole world. It is emphasized that a book by Samuel, a simple political issue already in the media evolves, repeats, enlarges with artificial intelligence performances. Therefore, a simple information can be misrepresented to the whole world and actions, riots and wars can break out. Samuel added, social media bots can be effective on all matters such as sport, fashion, food, etc. Thus, modern propaganda will evolve with artificial intelligence (Woolley, & Howard 2018).

Modern propaganda used to express itself globally with developing technology. In future, modern propaganda will both spread the world with technology and imitate people with artificial intelligence. Even, modern propaganda will spread a single culture to the world with movies and TV series. It will make propaganda against those who do not believe in that culture. Thus, it can gather people around it and there will be propaganda wars in the future. It is emphasized that in a book by Kammen, there will be one culture, one faith and one nation in future with the developing alternative media. Cinema, books, media, magazines and consequently areas of interest will be shared worldwide. Those who

resist this assimilation will find the whole world against them (McGillion, 2020). All in all, modern propaganda is evolving and is using all methods it can use. With the developing alternative media and technology, modern propaganda would spread all around the world. It will use artificial intelligence and the modern propaganda will not only spread events, but also will affect people's decision making.

CONCLUSION

Propaganda has been beginning to evolve in societies after the 20th century. While propaganda grew stronger, Great Wars broke out and countries used modern propaganda on their societies. Major and global countries succeeded in evolving their societies so the whole World was affected as for these global countries. After the Great Wars, some ideologies started to emerge because most countries have been strongly affected and changed drastically. Firstly the Marshall plan entered into force and the USA has begun to provide economic aid to anticommunist countries in Europe. Against this too, Soviet continued to evolve their societies with communist propagandas. When the world has taken a little stress out, civil right movements started to get stronger. Societies in the 60's and 90's especially wanted to use modern propaganda to make their voice heard. Therefore, societies have begun to make worldwide impacts and started to influence the authorities. Today, advancing technology has made modern propaganda stronger. Televisions, music, films, series and especially social media started to direct people. Modern propaganda is affecting the world and some countries are using it like war. In the future, modern propaganda can polarize people across some ideological ideas and will use it to start wars. With the further development of technology, ideas will be in everyone's pocket within seconds. In this way, one text and event will be enough to build huge and zealous armies.

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